

Female Teacher's Perception to Recruitment in Male Elementary Schools, A Social Review

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 12, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 15, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Gender Disparity, Feminism, Harassment, Social Constraints, Muslim Society, Professional Issues</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5573180</p>	<p><i>Since its inception till date education policies in Pakistan could not meet its objectives. Educational policy designs proved false lab experiments. Yet another example of this failure was identified in the form of inducting female educators in male elementary schools as per the 2005 educational policy. The major objective of this research was to perceive the social and professional problems of female elementary educators teaching in male schools. Census sampling techniques were used to collect data from the respondents. A survey was designed to collect data from the participants. The retrieved data from the participant was fed into SPSS and descriptive statistic like mean and standard deviation was used to analyses respondent perceptions about the variable of the study. Major findings were: The majority of the respondents agreed that female teachers feel difficulty in coordinating with Male staff. Most of the respondents agreed that the non-availability of separate washrooms is a problem for female teachers in boys' schools. Female teachers agreed that they feel lonely in boys' elementary schools. The government may develop the policy to appoint females as heads of those boys' elementary schools where female teachers have been appointed.</i></p>

Introduction

Elementary education is the foundation for the development of every citizen. Elementary education plays a vital role in students' future (Trivedi 2013). In this sense, the quality and standards of education are strongly associated with the quality and effectiveness of its teachers. Unfortunately, in Pakistan, very little attention has been paid to the education sector in general and the recruitment of quality teachers in particular. Resultantly, Pakistan has one of the lowest literacy rates and quality educations (Farooq 1990). According to the recruitment policy of Punjab (2005-2006), female candidates can also apply in boys Primary or Elementary Schools. Because it is discussed in Punjab Education Policy (2005-2006) which was announced in December 2005 that female candidates were eligible to apply for the posts of ESE and SESE in boys primary and elementary schools in addition to all categories of posts in girls schools (2005). Female teachers working in schools faced a variety of problems. These problems arose from societal norms (family and relatives). Pakistan being an Islamic state bounds some obligations on female followers. Major among these restrictions is the open mixing of male and female genders. It is considered a sin (sunnah) to work with male members. Keeping in mind this religious restriction the female educators faced social constraints while leaving their doorstep. To work in a co-administrative system they need to take permission of their male family members (Islam 1997). Pakistan is a male dominant society where the head of the house is considered to be male like all other Muslim countries (Bhattacharya 2014). Training delivered to the females in Pakistan is that of a recessive and fearful being (Darr, Small et al. 2016). Women are psychologically, socially, and mentally treated as weakling (Shaw 2016). She is taken as a symbol of honor for the family's grace. Her collective consciousness from childhood is developed to keep aloof from her male counterparts and to observe Hijab (Zafar, Sathar, et al. 2019). Such restriction and taboos are prevailing in society which produces an open inhibition and this becomes part of a female personality (Ali, Ishtiaq, et al. 2013). These factors come into action when she accidentally or by choice comes out to earn wages. The close-mindedness of the cultural values, societal norms, and mental development of males makes it difficult for the woman to work properly in such setups where male and female colleagues had to work together (Ashra 2013). A professional woman in Pakistan is not given its status by society especially a woman who works with the male foils is considered to be degraded in the vicinity (Halai 2011, Ashra 2013). Teaching is a profession where one has to give his or her hundred percent and this could be done only when there is mental satisfaction given to that person (Noureen 2011). Female elementary teachers are less paid and their congenial condition is so poor that it seemed quite difficult to cope up with the odds and oddities of the society and to work in a non-conducive environment full of males (Bradley and Saigol 2012). On the other hand, the male colleagues feel her personal property and show less regard and respect to their female colleagues. The male head of the school holds pressure and keeps female colleague in a state where she is unable to work properly and give

her best. Moreover, family check and balance keeps female teachers under pressure and they feel themselves in a dungeon (Ahmad, Said et al. 2014). They are arrested in the shackles of the social and ethical bars and escape from this jail seemed impossible to them. They live a life where no hope comes and, in the end, either they transfer themselves from that male school or resign the job due to bullying and harassment of the societal fears or pressure from their family. All these indictments show the bizarre condition of the female elementary teachers with which they live their professional careers (Zahra, Yasin, et al. 2021).

Political influences, fewer facilities, frequent transfers are problems for female teachers. Far-flung area transfer also causes problems for elementary school teachers because accommodation facilities and transportation many kinds of issues are present (Farooq and Kai 2017). Society expectations and cultural & social beliefs are formed gender dynamics and gender traditional roles male and female (Ranjha, Shah, et al. 2018).

Literature review

Elementary education

The teaching profession is considered to be a prophetic profession in Islam. The first and foremost teacher of the world and for Muslims, the Holy Prophet Muhammad (P.U.H) said, "I am sent but as a teacher". «إنما بُعثت معلماً» In the light of this Hadith Mubarak, it is evident that a teacher is a person who can develop the powers of transferring knowledge with his teaching styles (Burbules 2000). All the developments and developed countries such as China, America, Germany, and many more received a place in the committee of nations through the reformation in educational systems (Dockry, Hall, et al. 2016). Education also provides reliable leadership to handle everyday problems amicably (Ahmed, Rauf, et al. 2013). Elementary schools need more learning time to provide for more teaching and learning. The Children learning in elementary school institutions come to know about good or bad in their lives. They learn their life skills at that age (Fisher, Godwin, et al. 2014). It is required that the system of elementary education may be improvised essentially as at that age the nation-building process is completed. Likewise, the teachers at this level should be given more mental relaxation and an environment where they can deliver their best to the future of the nation (Shabbir, Wei, et al. 2014). The teachers at this age are required to deliver basic life skills to the students and help them to convey their views and express their thoughts about daily life. It is time that learners may be molded towards the national aspiration and skillful at an early age. Pakistan's education accommodates approximately 36 million students in schools 2020/21 (Zakir, Qureshi, et al. 2020). Of these, 5,556,186 students were being studied in elementary education levels in Pakistan schools in 2020 (Kamran, Nasreen, et al. 2020).

Recruitment Policy

Since its freedom on 14th August 1947, half a century passed away but still, Pakistan remained largely a low literacy country in the world. Approximately, near about two-thirds of the population and 80 percent of rural women are still illiterate. Most of the children are between the age of five to nine are not going to school (ibid). The first educational conference of Pakistan was held in November 1947. The outcome of this conference stressed the development of training institutes for female teachers. The statement showed that the female teachers' training should be established for the training of the teachers (Hamidullah 2004). The special features that came under discussion in the National Commission of Education 1959, were that all the students of 6-11 age groups should go to schools for education for 10 years (Hamidullah 2004). The third education policy of Pakistan, 1972 focused to increase the enrollment of women's education especially, in rural areas. Education will be functional at the elementary level (ibid). In the educational policy 2005-2006 the government of Punjab approved recruitments against the clauses of the 1972 educational policy which collided with the vacant posts of female teaching staff (Punjab 2005).

The enforcement of these clauses regarding policy guidelines about the placement of female educators in male elementary schools arouses variant issues for female teachers. Some of these issues are: 1- Females educators faced the problem of separate washrooms in the male schools. 2- Transport facilities, 3- a place of prayer, etc. (Rashid and Maharashi 2015). Education changes the population of a country into useful humans and it works as an agent of positive change. The teacher community is most financially poor in our society; they are often looking for other sources of earning (Shah, Khan, et al. 2014). Although govt. has done much for teachers but still, there is a need for many efforts to overcome these problems.

The objective of the study

This study is designed to understand the problems of female teachers who are working in boys' schools. So, the objectives of the study were:

- 1- To evaluate the problems of gender differences faced by female teachers at male schools
- 2- To identify satisfaction level of interaction of male and female teachers in co setting at elementary school level.
- 3- To examine social issues faced by female teachers teaching at boys' elementary schools.

Research questions

1. To what extent did the female teachers face problems while interacting with male colleagues?

2. To what extent are the female teachers feel satisfied while delivering lessons in boys' schools?
3. To what extent are female teachers encountering social problems while working in boys' schools?

Research design

This research was descriptive and cross-sectional. All-female teachers who are working in boys' elementary schools in District Pattoki (Punjab) Pakistan were included in the population of the study. There are 61 such schools where female teachers have been appointed. 93 female teachers have been appointed in 61 schools. To select the sample from the population census sampling techniques were used for 93 female teachers. A semi-Structured Survey was designed to understand the problems of female teachers who are working in boys' elementary schools in District Pattoki and was named a Questionnaire for female teachers (QFT) in the study. The researchers conduct the research personally and answered the difficulties faced during the understanding of the QFT. The questionnaires were received and tabulated. The data was fed to SPSS to get the results numerically and they were interpreted for the use of common readers.

Theoretical Framework

The research dealt with the perception of the female teachers about their job satisfaction in the male elementary school so attribution theory (Kelley and Michela 1980) was used to assess the sensitivity of the female teachers teaching in the male schools. The attribution theory deals with the interpretation of the feeling of human beings about behavioral issues (Martinko, Harvey, et al. 2011). It is a process in which an individual stipulates his or her corporeal imprints so s/he might be able to tell about his or her working environment. This theory helped the researchers in the observation of what the reality of the situation was not the reality itself (Saleem and Ghani 2019). In this way, the outcome of this research was observed which described what the environment originally was which might be interpreted wrongly by the person who is delivering in that environment. This theory brought into light the hidden situations of the perceivers (Female Teachers) philosophically. Social situations, experiences, expectations, and similarities which are basic traits of the attribution theory came under discussion. The attribution theory promulgated internal and external forces pinching the perceivers (Female teachers) as an external factor caused due to societal pressure which they are facing (Saleem and Ghani 2019). They are under the pressure of the Halo effect which they have conceived on the footings of their single characteristic (Behrmann 2019). On the implementation of this theory on the perceivers it was found out that the performance expectation, ethnic profiling, and employment efforts were the three hidden effects that collectively imparted the perceivers (Islam and Asadullah 2018).

Data Analysis & Interpretation

Table 01 *Female Teachers' Interaction Problems with Male Colleagues*

Item	S.D	M	Rank
Male teachers cooperate with you.	1.28	2.76	4
There is difficulty in coordinating with staff male	0.87	3.68	1
You can discuss your problems with male colleagues.	1.32	3.13	2
You feel insecure from male staff.	.98	2.34	5
You feel embarrassed by male colleagues.	1.05	2.98	3

The table reflected interaction problems of female appointees of boys' schools with male colleagues. The mean scores of interaction problems with male colleagues ranged from 3.68 to 2.34. The findings reveal that female teachers (Mean = 3.68; S.D = 0.87) felt interaction problems at a high level with male colleagues in boys' schools. This problem was ranked first among the interaction problems of female teachers in boys' schools. Female teachers disagreed (Mean = 2.34; S.D = 0.98) that they felt insecure from male staff.

Table 02 *Female Teachers' Interaction Problems with Heads*

Item	S.D.	M	Rank
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The Head is gender-biased while taking decisions.	1.04	3.51	1
You feel fear from the head.	1.22	2.56	4
You feel hesitation to convey some of your problems to the male head.	1.20	2.88	3
You feel that it is very difficult for a female teacher to go alone in the office of the headteacher.	1.29	2.99	2
Sometimes you feel that your headteacher abuse you sexually.	1.26	1.94	5

The table indicated interaction problems of female teachers with heads. Female teachers agreed that the heads were biased while taking decisions. The mean scores of female teachers' interaction problems with heads ranged from 3.51 to 1.94. Female teachers agreed ($M = 3.51$; $S.D = 1.04$) that head-teachers of dual-gender schools were biased while taking decisions. Most of the female teachers ($M = 1.94$; $S.D = 1.26$) disagreed that headteachers harass them sexually.

Table 03 *Female Teachers' General Academic Problems in Boys' Schools*

Item	S.D.	M	Rank
Teaching biological science is difficult to teach in boys' schools.	1.22	3.46	1
You have difficulty in maintaining discipline in boys' classrooms.	1.44	3.18	3
You feel difficulty in managing extracurricular activities in school.	1.07	3.32	2

This table shows the general academic problems of female teachers. Female appointees agreed ($M=3.46$, $S. D=1.22$) that science subject is difficult to teach in boys' schools. The mean scores of the other two statements were at a moderate level, it means that female teachers remained undecided about the difficulties of discipline maintaining and managing extracurricular activities. The mean scores of general academic problems ranged from 3.46 to 3.18.

Table 04

Perceptions of Female Teachers about the General Social Problems of the Society

Items	S.D.	M	Rank
You face social problems while teaching in a boys' school.	1.21	3.44	1
You have listened to negative remarks from your siblings (brother/ sister) just because of your job in boys' school.	1.12	2.46	2

The table reveals the perceptions of female teachers about their general social problems in society. According to measuring criteria, female appointees were undecided about social problems while teaching in boys' schools. They also remained undecided about listening to negative remarks from their siblings.

Table 05

Miscellaneous Problems of Female Appointees in Boys Schools

Item	S.D.	M	Rank
You feel lonely in boys' schools.	1.59	3.86	2
No availability of a separate washroom is a problem for you.	1.48	4.04	1
You feel insecure sitting late in school.	1.04	3.33	3
You are satisfied in boys' school.	1.29	2.89	4

The above table shows the miscellaneous problems of female appointees in boys' schools. The mean scores of miscellaneous problems of female teachers ranged from (4.04 to 2.89). Female teachers were at a high level, which means that female teachers of boys' schools were agreed ($M=4.04$, $S.D=1.48$) and were ranked at first level that separate washrooms are not available in boys' schools and this is a big problem for them. Female appointees feel loneliness ($M = 3.86$; $S.D = 1.59$) in boys' schools. Female teachers disagreed ($M = 2.89$; $S.D = 1.29$) that they were satisfied in boys' schools.

Findings

Based on the data retrieved from the respondents following findings were educed.

The respondents identified that they felt communicative incapability with the male colleagues who are teaching with them as they are not used to talk with males. Secondly, it is prohibited socially to interact with other male counterparts. They are not socially trained to teach in a co-teaching environment so they perceived that it is sin and against the teachings of Islam and their cultural values and societal norms. It is evident from the statements recorded by the elementary school teachers that they fell consciously ill after performing their duties and their mental and psychological condition seemed quite insecure. Society and their family take it below their honor and family pride and dignity while sending them to male school staff and students. This situation produced among them fear, a shudder from their colleagues and especially heads. They perceived themselves as a minority and they thought the decisions made by the head is biased as they are neglected and the decision-making process is made by the head who is male and he derogated them by thinking of them as weaklings. The head treated them dually and an imparted wall of gender differences is developed among colleagues where they are unable to breathe well. They keep a distance from their male counterparts and in staff meetings, they have to sit silently and their opinion did not matter a lot to the heads and their colleagues.

Along with these issues they perceived some academic problems as well. Data identified that female teachers appointed to teach boys in the schools faced difficulty to explain some subjects like biological science as they feel shy to explain some of the topics before students such as; reproductive system, human organs, and others. At the same time, they found that it is not easy for them to control the boys to maintain the discipline of the classroom as compared with their male foils. They were not included in extracurricular activities and if they are given they felt that they were not able to do it properly. The reason behind this was the behavior of the boys who did not cooperate with them as they do with male teachers. The major pressure which they felt on them was about the societal background from which they belong as people in their surroundings do not think it proper to visit male school and work along with the male. So they are taunted and many times they felt ashamed of the remarks delivered to them. They are called bad names for joining the school where even they do not have a female washroom, prayer room, and privacy.

Discussion

The respondents' perceptions about interaction problems of female teachers with male colleagues were at a high level. Because there are mostly one or two female appointees working with male colleagues, therefore, this may be one out of many reasons for female teachers to have interaction problems in schools. Mostly, male colleagues were not cooperative with them. Culture, family backgrounds, and system of education may be the main factors of these problems. At primary, middle, and high levels, male and female students studying in different schools. Therefore, this difference may be the main reason for interaction problems. Female teachers were undecided that they can discuss their problems with male colleagues. Female appointees hesitate to interact with male colleagues and they may also have fear of scandal by other male colleagues or the other members of society. It may be the main hindrance to male and female interaction problems. In the same way, male teachers may also have fear of scandal by colleagues or the other members of society. According to PEC results of the 5th and 8th classes, most of the students failed each year in science subjects. The majority of the students were not mature enough particularly at the primary level. A female teacher may feel hesitant in describing some science topics openly because of gender differences. Some female teachers do have not much knowledge about science subjects because they have no specialization in a science subject. It is also the main factor for the difficulty of teaching science. Female teachers feel lonely in boys' schools because only one or two female teachers are working with male colleagues in boys' schools. They can't talk or share their problems with male colleagues due to the danger of scandal.

Conclusion

In the light of the discussion and data retrieved from the respondents following conclusions were made based on the opinions from the respondents. There are problems for the female teachers and they feel themselves misfit in the teaching environment. In this case, they are not able to perform well or a hundred percent due to certain inhibitions such as; societal pressure, gender biasedness, mental stress, fear of being watched by male colleagues, and lack of a professional environment. Female teachers have interaction problems with male colleagues and heads like coordination or collaboration. Most of the respondents perceived it at a high level. The

female respondents reported that overall female teachers had problems while delivering lessons. Female teachers agreed that teaching science is difficult for them in boys' elementary schools. The female respondents reported that female teachers feel lonely in boys' schools and they feel that separate washrooms are necessary for them in boys' elementary schools.

We are a closed society where women are treated as weak individuals. Male dominance in all fields makes female counterparts less competitive and this develops a perception of failure and degradation among the female teachers teaching at boys' schools. The government should direct the high-ups to visit and look for the benefit of the female teachers. The section of the schools may be developed for the protection of female teachers.

Recommendation

1. The government may develop the policy to appoint females as heads of those boys' elementary schools where female teachers have been appointed. So that females may feel comfortable sharing their problems and interacting with their heads. Special training may be organized for the staff both male and female of those schools where females have been appointed as teachers to train them for enhancing interaction with each other.
2. Heads may arrange male teachers to teach science subjects in boys' elementary schools. This may be the solution to the problem of female teachers. The special workshop about teaching science may be managed for female staff.
3. Separate washrooms may be managed for male and female teachers in boys' schools. So that female teachers feel comfortable in boys' elementary schools.

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